

Dissertation Title

Isolation and Selection of Petroleum-Degrading Local Microorganisms and Biosurfactant Production

SeyedehZahra Hashemi, Alzahra University, Mar. 2024

10.5281/zenodo.17248206

Abstract:

Due to their structural characteristics, biosurfactants have promising physicochemical properties make them interesting molecules for various applications in different fields, including the bioremediation of hydrocarbon-contaminated sites. In particular, the bioproduction of surfactin, one of the best known microbially synthesized biosurfactants, is of interest to researchers. In this study, the ability of wild-type isolates to degrade crude oil and produce biosurfactants was investigated. Using screening assays include crude oil degradation as sole carbon source, oil spreading, droplet collapse, hemolysis of blood cells, insoluble ion pair formation, and emulsification index, the ability of isolates to degrade crude oil and produce biosurfactants were investigated. The concentration and structure of the biosurfactants and the degradation of the hydrophobic substrate were investigated using HPTLC, LC-ESI-MS/MS and GC-MS/MS methods, respectively. Among isolates obtained from various samples contaminated with crude oil, one isolate named P7, derived from wastewater, demonstrated positive outcomes across all screening assays. 16S rRNA specified strain P7 as *Bacillus subtilis*. With another strain isolated from crude oil-contaminated soil samples introduced in our previous work as *B. subtilis* ZH1. Using HPTLC and spectrometric determination, the lipopeptides surfactin and fengycin were detected for both strains, while no iturin family identified. Based on LC-ESI-MS/MS analysis, the strains showed similar chromatographic profiles containing unknown lipopeptides, such as unknown surfactin, which required NMR confirmation. Supplemented cultivation with hexadecane as a hydrophobic inducer showed a higher biomass formation for the strains ZH1 (26%) and P7 (33%) compared to the control strain DSM10T. The corresponding hexadecane degradation efficiencies were 34.03, 39.89, and 4.53% for *B. subtilis* strains ZH1, P7, and DSM10T. The presence of hydrophobic inducer in the supplemented cultivations showed interestingly changes in the production of lipopeptides, decreasing in surfactin and improving in fengycin productivity. Contrary to common opinion, hydrophobic inducer did not have a stimulating effect on surfactin bioproduction.

Keywords: *Bacillus Subtilis*, Biosurfactant, Fengycin, Hydrophobic Inducer, Surfactin.